

Project	GUTTA
Work Package number	1
Work Package title	Project management and coordination of activities
Deliverable number	1.2.4
Deliverable title	Progress report #4
Deliverable Responsible Partner	CMCC
Deliverable Lead authors	Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)
Deliverable Contributors	Paola Agostini (CMCC)
Deliverable due date	2021-06-30
Deliverable latest review date	2021-09-29
Comments	

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Project progress.....	2
2.1 General achievements	2
2.2 Pending issues	3
2.3 Status metrics	3
2.3.1 Financial absorption.....	4
2.3.2 Technical implementation.....	8
3. Conclusions	9

1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project progress in fulfilment of its specific and communication objectives during the reporting period ranging from 2020-07-01 to 2021-06-30, corresponding to RP4 and RP5 altogether. Please note that full technical and financial information is declared on SIU platform and the present report just represents an overview of related contents.

It includes reference to project deliverables of this period as well as documentation of major unforeseen delays and achievements.

When not re-defined here, shortcuts refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3667198

2. Project progress

The report is organized into General achievements (Sect.2.1), unforeseen Issues (Sect.2.2), and a summary of project status by means of key metrics (Sect.2.3).

2.1 General achievements

During the 12 months of the present report, significant management, communication, and technical progress was achieved by the GUTTA project.

Management

Besides ordinary day-to-day management, the first part of the current period was used for collecting inputs and feedback on the Major Change (MC) of GUTTA. Bi-lateral meetings with each PP were held starting from August 2020 till March 2021. The Advisory Board (EMSA) was also involved. Then, a multilateral SC meeting was held at the end of April 2021 for presenting a consolidated draft of the MC documents and asking for approval. The MC was eventually submitted in May and approved by the MA in June 2021. It includes both technical and financial changes for dealing with the project extension by 12 months, the changes in the external framework due to COVID-19 and its impacts on maritime activities, and the reorganization of responsibilities within the GUTTA partnership.

Communication

Besides providing updates on project progress on various social media, in this period a peer-reviewed paper was submitted and published, a webinar with an external guest (Cacciapaglia) was run and its recording made available on you tube (achieving record visualizations for CMCC webinars), an online dissemination event was held with about 100 high-school students, and preparation of a high-level Interreg multi-project event was started together with the METRO and E-CHAIN projects. Furthermore, GUTTA activity was relaunched by the respected “Blue and Green” section of the Italian newspaper *repubblica.it*.

Technical

The 12 months included in this report were quite important for progress on SO1. For SO1, data collected at UniZd simulator were processed by CMCC for extracting a ferry response function at sea. This function is a part of the new VISIR-2 model which can compute least-CO2 routes in presence of waves and currents. The model features and preliminary results were described in a peer-reviewed journal paper. The model is also being used in the operational service under construction which will feed the “eco-route” tool of GUTTA. In reference to SO2 and SO3, the work mainly consisted in data collection (CIMIS, AIS) and planning of activities in the remainder of the project.

2.2 Pending issues

During the current period, there were two main reasons of concern:

- So far, AdSP could provide limited technical contributions to the project. However, AdSP announced hiring a new human resource for providing support in the implementation of GUTTA. In RP5, for the first time, they reported some costs;
- CSA announced that its Director will leave the organization in Sep.2021. This might produce delays and reductions in CSA engagement, as this human resource is not planned to be replaced in the short term. Unfortunately, this information was provided to the LP only after submission of the MC.

2.3 Status metrics

The status of the project is monitored through both financial and technical implementation data, as reported in the following two subsections.

2.3.1 Financial absorption

The financial absorption, inclusive of implementation gaps, both at WP and activity level, is summarized in Fig.1-5. The titles of the activities are provided in Tab.1.

With respect to previous reports of this kind, we have updated the definitions of the fractions as follows:

- Done: cumulative absorption since project start, divided by planned cumulative absorption;
- Gap: difference between to-be-spent and actually-spent budget in given RP, divided by planned cumulative absorption. Negative values means overspending;
- Remainder: complement to 1 of the sum of done and gap.

Furthermore, in this annual progress report, information relative to both RP4 and RP5 is included. They are defined as:

- RP4: 4th reporting period (2020-07-01 to 2020-12-31)
- RP5: 5th reporting period (2021-01-01 to 2021-06-30)

Information on the budget breakdown at the level of budget lines and other details can be found in D.1.4.4.

Figure 1 WP1 implementation status at the end of both RP4 (upper row) and RP5 (lower row).

Figure 2 WP2 implementation status at the end of both RP4 (upper row) and RP5 (lower row).

Figure 3 WP3 implementation status at the end of both RP4 (upper row) and RP5 (lower row).

Figure 4 WP4 implementation status at the end of both RP4 (upper row) and RP5 (lower row).

Figure 5 WP5 implementation status at the end of both RP4 (upper row) and RP5 (lower row).

Table 1 Activities executed in RP4 and RP5.

A. number	Activity title
1.1	Start-up activities
1.2	Day-to-day project management, coordination and internal communication
1.3	Steering and monitoring of the project implementation
1.4	Financial management
2.1	Start-up activities
2.2	External communication
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders
3.1	Input data collection
3.2	Initial data analysis and planning
4.1	Emissions and routing models

4.2	MRV - data collection guidance
4.3	Preliminaries for new CB maritime routes
4.4	Eco-routes DSS
5.1	Validation and demonstration

The overall implementation rate is defined as the actual cumulative absorption compared to the planned absorption. At the end of RP5, this indicator read 74.1%.

More information on the breakdown of the budget absorption can be found in the financial report of RP4 and RP5, corresponding to deliverable D.1.4.4.

2.3.2 Technical implementation

The progress advancement is monitored through the status of the Deliverables of RP4 and RP5 in Tab.2.

Table 2 Status of implementation of deliverables of the present period completed.

	D. number	D. title	Month due	PP in charge
1	1.2.4	Progress report #4	30	CMCC
2	1.4.4	Financial report #4	30	CMCC
3	4.1.1	Report on parametrization of vessel CO2 emissions in terms of environmental state variables	20	UniZd
4	4.1.2	Report on VISIR software advancements	20	CMCC
5	4.2.1	Guidance document on implementation of Monitoring and Reporting of MRV	20	CSA
6	4.2.2	Report on extraction activity of ferry AIS data	20	MMPI
7	4.3.1	Report on extraction activity of CIMIS data	20	MMPI

All RP4 and RP5 deliverables are complete and were submitted to the SIU system.

3. Conclusions

The implementation of GUTTA project activities was monitored by the present report.

The overall financial absorption is about 74% of planned, might look quite satisfactory given that 71% of the extended project lifetime (30 out of 42 months) has elapsed. However, underspending from two PPs still needs to be recovered.

The last year implied a major effort to amend the GUTTA project from both financial and technical viewpoint with respect to the impacts of the pandemic.

The largest part of the technical work was devoted to deliver with respect to the programme output indicator “4.101 - Improved multimodal transport services”, which is covered by GUTTA SO1. However, crucial progress on SO2 and SO3 was also performed and should become visible in the coming RPs.